

Original Article

Navigating the New Normal: Strengthening Education and Counselling through Technology in Underprivileged Pakistani Schools

Ahmed Saya¹ & Mahnoor Shaikh²

¹ PhD Scholar, Department of Education, Institute of Business Management

² M.Phil. Student, Department of Education, Institute of Business Management

Abstract

This study explores the impact of COVID-19 on underprivileged schools in Pakistan, focusing on how they managed education during lockdowns, the adaptations introduced, and their preparedness for future crises. Using purposive sampling, data was collected through semi structured interviews, observations, and focus groups. Six principals and thirty-six teachers from six schools were interviewed, alongside five student focus groups of 8–12 participants each. Findings revealed that the pandemic severely disrupted education and emphasized the urgent need to integrate technology for sustaining learning in marginalized contexts. Despite some digital awareness, limited resources and lack of availability of technology hindered adoption of remote learning. The study also identified significant counselling and psychosocial support needs among students, particularly related to anxiety, demotivation, and isolation, with low-cost interventions offering partial solutions. Overall, the research underscores that unless technology is systematically embedded and students are equipped with digital skills, educational continuity and effective counselling in underprivileged schools will remain out of reach.

Keywords: Counselling; Digital divide; Educational continuity; Post pandemic education; Technology integration; Underprivileged schools

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education systems worldwide, but its effects were severe in underprivileged schools of Pakistan (Ullah & Ali, 2022). School closures exposed inequities which were already in existence, with limited access to digital tools and counselling resources widening the educational divide between privileged students and underprivileged students (González & Bonal, 2021; UNESCO, 2020). While some schools adopted temporary strategies to sustain learning, challenges such as lack of technological infrastructure, absence of formal counselling services, and students' limited access to technological devices hindered effective transition during lockdowns (Vegas, 2020; Yun, 2023). These circumstances highlighted the urgent need to embed technology into the education system and to strengthen psychosocial support mechanisms to ensure counteractive measures in case such crisis occurs in future (García & Weiss, 2020; Guppy et al., 2022).

Globally, the post-pandemic discourse emphasized the integration of technology and counselling in education as a prerequisite to continue teaching and learning (Sato et al., 2023; Vegas et al., 2021). Digital platforms, Education technologies, and hybrid learning models have emerged as feasible solutions to mitigate learning interruptions, while counselling support has been recognized as imperative for addressing student anxiety, isolation, and demotivation (Li, 2023; Ossiannilsson, 2022). However, the digital divide remains the main concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where infrastructure, affordability, and digital literacy are limited (Inegbedion, 2021; Wamuyu, 2017). In Pakistan, these challenges are even more

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

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How to Cite:

Saya, A., & Shaikh, M. (2024). Navigating the New Normal: Strengthening Education and Counselling through Technology in Underprivileged Pakistani Schools. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 1(2), 111-122.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17132324>

pronounced in underprivileged schools, where constrained resources and lack of systematic support impede both technological adoption and psychosocial services (Ghani, 2024; Hamdani et al., 2021).

Technology and counselling are essential components of resilient education systems, despite this, schools in underprivileged Pakistani communities continue to face systemic barriers (Ghani et al., 2024; Hamdani et al., 2021). The pandemic revealed deep-rooted inequalities: most underprivileged schools lacked the infrastructure for online learning, while many students had no access to digital devices or internet connectivity (Hyder et al., 2024). Additionally, the absence of counselling facilities caused mental health issues among students causing anxiety, demotivation, and social isolation (Savarese et al., 2020). These limitations not only interrupted academic progress during school closures but also raised concerns regarding the ability of underprivileged schools to withstand future crises (Shahzad, 2024). Addressing these gaps requires a context-specific understanding of how technology and counselling can be realistically integrated into resource-constrained educational settings (Akram et al., 2021).

This study holds significance as it captures the lived realities of principals, teachers, and students in underprivileged Pakistani schools during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. By documenting their experiences, it provides valuable insights into the resilience and vulnerabilities of marginalized education systems. The findings contribute to the global post-pandemic discourse, identifying and investigating how schools in marginalized communities navigated the pandemic and how technology and counselling can be leveraged to ensure educational continuity in future crises. Moreover, the study emphasizes low-cost, contextually relevant interventions that can inform policymakers, educators, and NGOs in designing sustainable strategies. By emphasizing technology and counselling as dual priorities, the research highlights their critical role in ensuring uninterrupted education and addressing the long-term wellbeing of students in resource-constrained environments.

Objectives and Research Questions

The present study seeks to examine how education and counselling in underprivileged Pakistani schools were reshaped by the COVID-19 crisis and how these institutions can build resilience for the future. Specifically, the research aims to explore the impact of the pandemic on students' educational experiences, identify barriers to the adoption of technology in marginalized contexts, and assess how counselling needs are being addressed in the post-pandemic era. To achieve these aims, the study is structured around the following research questions:

1. How did the COVID-19 pandemic reshape the educational experiences of students in marginalized communities in Pakistan?
2. What barriers do underprivileged schools face in adopting technology for continued learning and support post-COVID?
3. How are the counselling needs of underprivileged students being addressed in the post-pandemic context?

Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic has generated a vast body of literature examining its disruptive effects on education worldwide. Scholars have highlighted how school closures accelerated pre-existing inequalities, particularly in marginalized communities where access to technology, teacher training, and psychosocial support was already limited (UNESCO, 2021; Schleicher, 2020). Beyond learning loss, research has also pointed to the emotional and social toll of prolonged isolation on students, emphasizing the dual challenge of sustaining academic continuity while safeguarding mental wellbeing (Harrison et al., 2022; OECD, 2021). In low- and middle-income countries, these issues are compounded by structural deficits in digital infrastructure, limited funding, and the absence of formal counselling systems (Dvorsky et al., 2023). Within this broader discourse, studies focused on Pakistan remain relatively scarce, especially those that integrate both educational and psychosocial dimensions in underprivileged schools.

COVID-19 and Educational Experiences in Marginalized Communities

Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic caused unprecedented disruption in education, affecting nearly 1.6 billion learners at the peak of school closures (UNESCO, 2021). Research shows that students from marginalized backgrounds were disproportionately impacted, as school closures limited access not only to academic resources but also to essential social support systems such as school meals and safe learning environments (World Bank, 2020). The shift to remote learning, while effective in some high-income contexts, widened inequalities in low-income communities where access to reliable internet, digital devices, and parental support was scarce (OECD, 2021; Pettalongi et al., 2024).

In South Asia, the pandemic exacerbated existing inequities in education systems marked by poverty, gender disparities, and rural-urban divides. Studies highlight that many children, particularly in rural and low-income households, experienced significant learning loss, disengagement, and higher risks of dropout due to prolonged closures (Aziz et al., 2021). Limited availability of affordable digital solutions and low teacher preparedness further hindered learning continuity in the region (Hyder et al., 2024).

In Pakistan, the pandemic exposed structural weaknesses in public education, especially in underprivileged schools (Ullah & Khan, 2023). While wealthier institutions transitioned to online platforms, schools in marginalized communities struggled with minimal infrastructure and negligible access to digital resources (Rehman et al., 2022). Pakistan already faced a severe education crisis prior to the pandemic, with an estimated 22.8 million children out of school, one of the highest figures globally (UNICEF, 2022). Literacy rates remain low, particularly among rural populations and girls, further widening inequities (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2021). The pandemic not only disrupted academic routines for those enrolled but also increased dropout risks, particularly for children at the margins of the education system. Parents, often with limited literacy themselves, were unable to support home-based learning (Jamil, 2021). Beyond academics, students reported feelings of isolation, demotivation, and anxiety, underscoring the urgent need for holistic approaches that combine educational continuity with psychosocial support (Passos et al., 2022).

Barriers to Technology Adoption in Underprivileged Schools

The rapid transition to online learning during the pandemic highlighted the central role of technology in sustaining education, but also revealed stark inequities. Globally, while high-income countries were able to adopt digital platforms, low- and middle-income nations struggled with issues of affordability, limited internet penetration, and lack of teacher preparedness (OECD, 2021; World Bank, 2020). Studies emphasize that the digital divide not only disrupted learning continuity but also reinforced existing socioeconomic gaps (United Nations, 2021).

In South Asia, digital adoption was constrained by weak infrastructure, frequent electricity shortages, and limited device ownership. Teachers, particularly in rural areas, lacked adequate training to use digital platforms, while many students had to share a single device among family members, leading to inconsistent participation in remote learning (Aziz et al., 2021).

In Pakistan, barriers to technology adoption in underprivileged schools are particularly severe. Internet penetration remains uneven, with rural areas significantly disadvantaged compared to urban centers (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority, 2021). The cost of smartphones, tablets, and data packages places digital learning out of reach for many low-income families. Teachers, often with little exposure to technology, struggled to adapt, and schools lacked structured professional development to bridge these gaps (Jamil, 2021). Moreover, infrastructural issues such as unreliable electricity, inadequate classroom facilities, and absence of computer labs further restricted the shift to blended or remote learning (Pettalongi et al., 2024). Although some low-cost solutions such as WhatsApp-based lessons, TV and radio broadcasts, and NGO-led initiatives were introduced, their reach and effectiveness were limited (Sahin & Shelley, 2020). These challenges suggest that unless technology is systematically embedded and supported by policy, underprivileged schools will remain unable to achieve sustainable digital integration (Vegas, 2020).

Counselling and Psychosocial Needs in Post-Pandemic Education

The pandemic not only disrupted academic learning but also triggered widespread psychosocial challenges among students worldwide. Studies indicate rising levels of stress, anxiety, isolation, and demotivation, particularly where prolonged school closures limited social interaction and support networks (OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2021). Counselling and psychosocial support have thus been recognized as critical to post-pandemic educational recovery, with many systems introducing tele-counselling, peer mentoring, and online wellbeing programs (WHO, 2020).

In developing contexts, however, counselling services remain scarce and often underfunded. Research in South Asia highlights the absence of formal school-based counselling structures, leaving teachers already overburdened with academic responsibilities to address students' emotional and behavioral needs informally (Aziz et al., 2021). The stigma associated with mental health further limits help-seeking behaviors, especially among adolescents. Counsellors provide sessions encouraging healthy thought processes that could help make positive decisions regarding emotional and professional concerns (Saya & Habib, 2023).

In Pakistan, counselling needs became particularly visible during the pandemic. Students in underprivileged schools reported increased levels of anxiety, demotivation, and social isolation as they struggled with disrupted routines and lack of structured guidance (Rehman et al., 2022). Yet, few schools had dedicated counsellors, and most lacked referral mechanisms for students requiring psychosocial support. Cultural taboos around mental health, combined with systemic neglect of counselling in educational policy, exacerbated the problem (Jamil, 2021). This underscores the urgent need for formal, scalable, and culturally sensitive counselling frameworks that can be embedded within underprivileged schools alongside technological integration.

Pandemic Era Teacher Training: Needs, Methods and Efficacy

The rapid transition to online platforms resulted in stress and inadequacy among existing teachers as they were not trained in remote teaching methodology (Reychav et al., 2023). Thus, numerous professional development programs were implemented, and digital platforms were adopted to support teachers in new technological competencies (Rehman et al., 2022; Reychav et al., 2023). Professional development focused on digital literacy, use of learning management systems, and online assessment (Mintii, 2023). Stressing on student engagement and motivation strategies guided teachers navigate the challenges of distance education comprehensively.

The impact of pandemic-driven teacher training programs has been shown to increase teachers' confidence, competence, and adaptability in managing online classrooms (Pozo-Rico et al., 2020). Teachers serve as first responders when students present mental health issues in classrooms yet feel inadequately prepared for this role (Gunawardena et al., 2024). Teachers, if trained appropriately can be frontline supporters towards students counselling and guidance (Ali & Ullah 2021).

Integrating Technology and Counselling for Educational Continuity

The literature collectively demonstrates that sustaining education in crises requires both technological innovation and psychosocial support. Empirical studies highlight that the integration of digital tools can significantly reduce learning disruptions when accompanied by strategies to address students' emotional wellbeing. For instance, Tsolou et al. (2021) found that blended learning models combining online and face-to-face methods enhanced resilience in disadvantaged European schools. Similarly, Onyema et al. (2020) reported that technology-driven interventions in Nigerian schools mitigated learning gaps but required parallel counselling support to maintain student motivation. In India, Jena (2020) observed that low-cost digital platforms, supplemented with peer-support mechanisms, enabled continuity in marginalized contexts. Studies in Kenya (Abuya et al., 2021) further revealed that psychosocial programmes delivered alongside digital learning helped reduce dropout risks in under-resourced communities.

In Pakistan, research has underscored similar challenges. Rehman et al. (2022) documented how teachers in low-income schools adopted WhatsApp-based learning but struggled with student disengagement due to stress and lack of devices. Jamil (2021) found that while NGO-led technology initiatives offered short-

term relief, they failed to address underlying counselling needs. Furthermore, a UNICEF (2022) report emphasized that without embedding structured psychosocial support into schools, underprivileged students remain at risk of long-term learning loss and mental health issues. Collectively, these findings highlight that technology and counselling cannot be treated in isolation. For underprivileged Pakistani schools, a dual strategy embedding affordable digital solutions and institutionalizing counselling frameworks is critical to achieving sustainable educational continuity in the post-pandemic era.

The literature demonstrates that the challenges of education in underprivileged schools during COVID-19 extend beyond digital divides to include psychosocial vulnerabilities. Global studies underscore the importance of coupling technology adoption with psychosocial support, as one without the other risks perpetuating inequities (Tsolou et al., 2021; Abuya et al., 2021). In Pakistan, where millions of children face compounded disadvantages due to poverty, gender, and systemic underinvestment (UNICEF, 2022), an integrated model that strengthens both educational technology and counselling support is critical. This dual focus not only enhances resilience against future crises but also builds pathways toward more equitable educational continuity in marginalized communities.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates how the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted education in underprivileged Pakistani schools, leading to both educational and psychosocial challenges. These challenges are partially mediated by teaching digital upskilling and low-cost interventions, which in turn contribute to desired outcomes of educational continuity, psychosocial wellbeing, and resilience.

Methodology

Study Design

Since the outbreak of Covid impacted the education sector in multidimension “The COVID19 has since continued to spread across the world with immediate and long term social economic effects on national economies and their individual citizens” and everyone had a different experience in education sector regarding it, therefore this study used a qualitative research method, which assumes that reality is what participants believe it to be. Being a qualitative researcher, I consider myself as an “instrument” in research because all observations, interpretations and analyses are filtered through my personal lens (Bhandari, 2020). Similarly, according to (Creswell & Miller,2000) a qualitative researcher ensures that the participants' opinions and beliefs are appropriately represented. Three semi structured interview questionnaires were developed: one for

school principals, other for the teachers and one for the focus group, having four open ended questions from teachers and principals and 5 open ended questions from focus group.

Open-ended questions allow participants to react in their own terms rather than presenting them with a fixed set of response possibilities. Open-ended questions are widely used in qualitative research approaches and exploratory studies. (Jackson and Trochim, 2002) comments that Open-ended questions not only assist researchers in gaining a better understanding of an issue, but they also produce an intriguing and complex text for analysis, as the text can span from a few phrases to a couple of paragraphs and contain a wide range of topics.

Data Collection Technique

Four different data collection techniques were used, notes through interviews, recording of interviews, observations and focus groups. All respondents agreed to being recorded, those who refused, were not interviewed. Identity of all respondents was kept confidential, and Prior permission was taken from them whether they are willing to give interviews.

Individual interviews were conducted from principals of six underprivileged schools, and four to six teachers were interviewed from each school, and a total of Thirty-Six teachers were interviewed. It was kept in mind that the Principals and teachers were from the same school.

Five focus groups of at least 8 – 12 students, were also conducted from these schools, after taking prior permission from them. It was also ensured that they have no objection to being recorded.

Sample

Purposive Sampling was used in this research. Purposive sampling, often called judgement sampling, is the deliberate selection of a participant based on personal qualities. It's a non-random technique that doesn't necessitate any underlying concepts or a set number of participants. According to (Bernard, 2002), the researcher decides what is the required information and then shortlist people who can and will provide the relevant details based on their firsthand knowledge or experience. (Creswell & Clark, 2011) further adds that this involves identification and selection of individuals or groups of individuals who have a know how about the concerned topic or research under consideration.

The Sample of School Principals, Teachers and focus group for this research was extracted keeping in mind the following characteristics:

- The school must be an underprivileged school.
- The fee of students per month must be less than or equals to PKR 1000 /-
- The school must be operational pre-covid, survived Covid and are operational post-covid
- The school must have more than 100 students
- The schools must have classes from nursery to matric.

Therefore, the sample was taken from six underprivileged schools of Karachi, Pakistan.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis is a technique for finding, analyzing, and interpreting meaning patterns ('themes') in qualitative data. This sort of Thematic Analysis stands out not just in terms of theoretical flexibility, but also in terms of research questions, sample size and composition, data collection method, and approaches to formation of analysis. In terms of participants' real experience, attitudes and viewpoints, behavior and practices, Thematic Analysis can be used to uncover patterns among and across data; 'experiential' research tries to learn what people think, feel, and do. (Braun & Clark, 2017). They went on to say that Themes provides accessible and systematic procedures for generating codes and themes from qualitative data.

In order to do qualitative analysis, we first generate codes. Codes are used to capture interesting data properties that are usually relevant to the research project in consideration. Themes are then generated from

the codes, which is a fundamental organizing thought - a shared core idea - underpins all patterns of meaning and coding. Themes provide a framework for organizing and summarizing the researcher's analytic observations. According to (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2013), the purpose of thematic analysis is to uncover and analyze the key, but not necessarily all, features of the data, using the study topic as a guide.

The data collected from the interviews was analyzed using the same methodology. Firstly, the interviews were transcribed into English, although they were conducted in Urdu, then they were coded, finally themes were derived from it and eventually analysis were made from the findings. Data were recorded and transcribed and the strategies of analysis recommended by Merriam (2009) were followed for analysis. The qualitative data was studied thoroughly, coding was done and later similar codes were developed into Five main themes; Lack of resources and technology – the digital divide, Digital literacy, Teachers training and learning platforms, students and teachers' motivation and Child Labour and school drop outs and Pre covid to post covid transition.

Findings and Discussion

Thematic analysis identified five interrelated themes: (1) lack of resources and technology, (2) digital literacy and teacher training, (3) teacher and student motivation, (4) child labour and dropouts, and (5) pre- to post-COVID transitions. A cross-cutting issue counselling and psychosocial support also emerged as an additional theme.

Lack of resources and technology: The digital divide

Resource scarcity was consistently described as the greatest barrier. Principals highlighted how poverty shaped families' access to technology: *“Most households have six or seven children and only one television. If there is a smartphone, it is with the father, who returns home late. How can children study like this?”* Another principal emphasized, *“This is a poverty-stricken area; families don't even have electricity and clean water, let alone internet or laptops.”*

Teachers echoed these constraints, noting they had to use their own devices: *“The school has one multimedia room for all classes. We had to pre-plan and wait our turn. For online teaching, I had to use my own phone, but students had no devices.”* Most teachers agreed that remote learning was not feasible: *“Our children cannot join online classes. They don't have internet, they don't have smartphones. For them, only face-to-face teaching works.”*

Students themselves gave candid accounts of deprivation: *“I have never used internet or a smartphone.”* Another student admitted, *“I thought Zoom meant making things big or small on the screen.”* Many described cramped living conditions: *“We live in one room with my whole family where could I attend class?”* These narratives affirm studies showing the digital divide widened inequalities during COVID-19 (UNICEF, 2021; Rehman et al., 2022).

Digital literacy and teacher training

With the new normal and digitalization taking place in education industry, the digital literacy has become imperative for teachers and students. The Teachers needs to be trained on how to use different digital platforms so that they can effectively teach even if there is lockdown implemented once again. It has been observed that teachers have been enthusiastic about learning technology, as they realize that it will benefit them in the long run. Despite resource gaps, COVID-19 compelled schools to adopt digital skills. Principals described significant shifts: *“Before, we wrote report cards by hand. Now everything is computerized. Teachers know Zoom and Google Classroom. Even tutorial videos from Sabaq.pk are part of lessons.”* One of the principals commented *“Teacher's training has now become mandatory part of our school culture.”* Another principal noted, *“Some of our teachers didn't know how to use email before COVID. Now they can search, share videos, and plan lessons online.”* Although COVID-19 presented many challenges, it had one positive effect: it pushed teachers out of their comfort zones. The pandemic demonstrated the need to work with digital technologies, and educators understood that without acquiring technological skills, they would not be able to fulfill their professional duties successfully. As it was pointed out by Pozo-Rico et al., 2020

that the impact of pandemic-driven teacher training programs increased teachers' confidence, competence, and adaptability in managing online classrooms

Teachers reported professional growth: *"YouTube was just entertainment before. Now I use it for tutorials to help my teaching."* Another added, *"We make WhatsApp groups with students and share videos, but many don't watch because they have no internet or their parents don't give them the phone."* Some also worried about misuse: *"Instead of watching lessons, students play games or watch dramas."*

Students who had limited exposure to digital platforms were excited: *"My brother takes Zoom classes, so I learned too."* Another said, *"Our teacher showed us videos from sabaq.pk in school, and it helped us understand better."* Yet many admitted, *"I don't know what Zoom is"* or *"I have never touched a computer."* These mixed experiences reflect how forced digital adoption created new skills but also reinforced inequities (Jamil, 2021).

Teacher and student motivation

Teacher and student motivation diverged sharply. Principals acknowledged difficulty recruiting qualified staff: *"Mainstream teachers won't come to these areas. We hire locals at very low pay, but they work hard for the cause of educating these children."* Another principal added, *"To motivate our teachers, we arrange training and even provide transport."*

Teachers felt empowered by new skills *"We are more computer literate, more confident"* but demoralized by learning loss. One lamented, *"Two years of lockdown wasted all our hard work. Students became lazy and forgot everything."* Another explained, *"We gave worksheets, but children made others do them. They learned nothing except cheating."*

Students openly admitted demotivation: *"After COVID, waking up early is so hard. We just became lazy."* Many spent lockdown playing outdoors or doing casual work. Yet a few showed resilience: *"I was fed up of sitting idle. I was excited to come back to school."* These accounts mirror global findings that student disengagement and teacher burnout were widespread in disadvantaged schools (Singh et al., 2020).

Child Labour and Dropouts

Economic pressures forced many children out of school permanently. One principal reported, *"Before COVID we had 405 students, now only 135 remain."* Another explained, *"Families moved back to villages or shifted children to madrassahs because they get free food there."*

Teachers confirmed: *"Some of my brightest students now work in workshops or shops. Parents say education cannot feed them."* Students also disclosed their realities: *"I earn PKR 200 per day at a car workshop."* A girl added, *"My brother left school to work at a tandoor."* Others noted friends who never returned after joining madrassahs. During lockdown when covid start spreading, many parents of underprivileged families became jobless. Since schools were closed, these school children were told to do jobs, beg on streets and were responsible to take care of their families in one way or the other. Many such children were permanently dropped out from schools so that they could be helping hands to their parents and earn for their family. And even when covid subsided, these children were not allowed to join back the schools. These findings align with UNICEF (2022), which reports that 22.8 million Pakistani children are out of school, many engaged in labour.

Pre- to post-COVID transition

Despite modest digital gains, schools largely admitted they would revert to closures or paper-based worksheets if faced with another lockdown. A principal reflected, *"Even after all this, if lockdown happens again, our only option is school closures or shifts. Online classes are beyond our reach."* Teachers agreed: *"We will do exactly what we did last time—prepare worksheets and wait."*

This reveals a sobering reality: while digital literacy improved, structural inequities mean underprivileged schools remain unprepared for future crises. As literature confirms, without systemic

investment, the digital divide will continue to exclude marginalized learners (World Bank, 2020; Azevedo et al., 2021).

Counselling and psychosocial support

Finally, counselling emerged as a critical unmet need. Principals noted widespread demotivation: *“Children had forgotten what they learned. We went door-to-door to bring them back.”* Teachers described students as *“disturbed, depressed, and less engaged”* and admitted, *“We are not trained counsellors. We don’t know how to manage serious issues.”*

Students themselves expressed emotional struggles: *“We felt lazy, we lost interest. Home was crowded and stressful.”* Others described being forced into work, which created both economic and psychological strain. Teachers tried informal support through WhatsApp check-ins or home visits, but barriers like shared phones and poor connectivity limited reach. The other complain that kept recurring was loneliness amongst students. Some students said that they really missed their peers. A student commented *“When I am in school I have friends, I talk, I enjoy there.”* Another said, *“At home I felt disconnected, as though no one was interested in me.”* They could not find any friends, communication, and games and thus felt invisible and excluded.

Nevertheless, low-cost strategies such as referral protocols, NGO partnerships, and digital check-ins show potential. As one teacher reflected, *“Even sending a simple message to students made them feel connected.”* These insights echo global recommendations for integrating psychosocial support into education recovery (WHO, 2021; UNICEF, 2022).

Conclusion

This study highlights how COVID-19 deepened educational inequalities in Pakistani underprivileged schools. Severe resource gaps and digital divides left families and schools unable to sustain remote learning, making face-to-face instruction the only viable option. At the same time, the crisis prompted modest gains in teacher digital literacy, though integration remained inconsistent due to systemic constraints.

Equally significant, the pandemic underscored the centrality of counselling. Students returned demotivated, anxious, and academically regressed, while teachers and principals assumed informal support roles without training or institutional backing. Although ad hoc practices such as WhatsApp check-ins and NGO collaborations showed promise, psychosocial services remain largely absent in Pakistan’s school system.

The findings affirm that educational recovery in marginalized communities cannot be limited to academic catch-up. Sustainable resilience requires three interdependent pillars: (1) bridging the digital divide through equitable access to devices and connectivity, (2) embedding opportunities for social connectedness in learning environments, and (3) institutionalizing counselling and psychosocial support. Without addressing these dimensions together, the goal of equitable and resilient post-pandemic education in underprivileged Pakistani schools will remain unattainable

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